

CIVAL: CLIMAAX in Valcerrina

Deliverable Phase I

Supporting Information 2: Results of public online surveys

Survey 1 targeting all residents of Valcerrina

n. of responses: 54

List of questions (in English)

1. Timestamp
2. Gender
3. Age group
4. Municipality of residence
5. Municipality of work
6. Highest level of education completed
7. Occupation
8. In the last 20 years, have you directly experienced one or more extreme climate events in the area where you live or work?
9. Which events did you directly experience?
10. How did this event affect you or your activity?
11. In your opinion, who is most exposed or vulnerable to climate risks in Valcerrina?
12. Do you feel part of a vulnerable category?
13. If yes, in what way do you think you are more at risk?
14. What does climate change mean to you?
15. How worried are you about the impact that climate change may have in Valcerrina?
16. How informed do you feel about the risks related to climate change in Valcerrina?
17. How much do you agree with the following statements about Valcerrina? [Average temperatures have increased]
18. How much do you agree with the following statements about Valcerrina? [Annual rainfall has decreased]
19. How much do you agree with the following statements about Valcerrina? [Nights are warmer]
20. How much do you agree with the following statements about Valcerrina? [Drought episodes are more frequent]

21. How much do you agree with the following statements about Valcerrina? [Forest fires are more frequent]
22. How much do you agree with the following statements about Valcerrina? [Torrential rains are more frequent]
23. How much do you agree with the following statements about Valcerrina? [Floods are more frequent]
24. How much do you agree with the following statements about Valcerrina? [Heatwaves are more frequent]
25. How much do you agree with the following statements about Valcerrina? [Frost or unusual snowfalls are more frequent]
26. How much do you agree with the following statements about Valcerrina? [Landslides and mudslides are more frequent]
27. Thinking about the future, which climate phenomena do you consider most relevant or concerning for the Valcerrina area?
28. In your opinion, what could be the consequences of these risks in the territory?
29. Which economic or social sectors do you consider most important for Valcerrina?
30. In your opinion, which of these sectors are most vulnerable to the effects of climate change?
31. Do you think climate change could change the way we live and work in Valcerrina in the coming years?
32. Would you like to share an observation or personal experience related to climate change in your area?
33. In your opinion, is your municipality ready to face the following climate risks? [Floods, heavy rains, periods of drought, landslides, heatwaves, frost/snow]
34. In your opinion, what kinds of interventions could help the Valcerrina area better cope with climate change?
35. In your work or daily life, have you already adopted any measures to adapt to phenomena such as drought, extreme heat, flooding, or fires?
36. If "Yes," please specify which ones:
37. What obstacles make adaptation difficult in your area or activity?
38. Would you be interested in participating in local activities on these topics? (e.g. public meetings, courses, pilot projects, activities with schools)
39. If yes, and you would like to participate, you can leave us your contact details (email or phone)
40. Would you like to propose an idea, project, or good practice that could help Valcerrina become more resilient to climate change?

Results (in Italian)

Genere

54 responses

Fascia di età

54 responses

Comune di residenza

54 responses

Comune di lavoro

54 responses

- Camino
- Cereseto
- Cerrina
- Gabiano
- Mombello Monferrato
- Moncestino
- Murisengo
- Odalengo Grande

▲ 1/4 ▼

Livello di istruzione più elevato completato

54 responses

- Nessun titolo di studio
- Licenza di scuola media
- Diploma di scuola superiore (es. liceo, tecnico, professionale)
- Diploma post-diploma o qualifica professionale (es. corsi regionali, ITS)
- Laurea triennale
- Laurea magistrale o specialistica
- Dottorato di ricerca o titolo post-laurea avanzato

Occupazione

54 responses

- Agricoltore o allevatore (attività agricola...)
- Artigiano o operaio specializzato (edili...)
- Lavoratore nel settore industriale o m...
- Impiegato o tecnico (uffici pubblici, azi...
- Professionista o lavoratore del settore...
- Commerciante, ristoratore o lavorator...
- Autonomo / lavoratore con partita IVA...
- Studente

▲ 1/3 ▼

Negli ultimi 20 anni, ha vissuto direttamente uno o più eventi climatici estremi nella zona in cui vive o lavora?

54 responses

Quali eventi ha sperimentato direttamente?

50 responses

Come ha influito su di Lei o sulla Sua attività questo evento?

50 responses

Secondo Lei, chi è più esposto o vulnerabile ai rischi climatici nella Valcerrina?

54 responses

Lei si sente parte di una categoria vulnerabile?

54 responses

Quanto Si sente preoccupato per l'impatto che i cambiamenti climatici potranno avere in Valcerrina?

54 responses

Quanto informato Si sente sui rischi legati al cambiamento climatico in Valcerrina?

54 responses

Quanto è in accordo con le seguenti affermazioni relative alla Valcerrina?

Pensando al futuro, quali fenomeni climatici ritiene più rilevanti o preoccupanti per il territorio della Valcerrina?

53 responses

Secondo Lei, quali potranno essere le conseguenze di questi rischi nel territorio?

54 responses

Quali settori economici o sociali ritiene più importanti per la Valcerrina?

54 responses

Secondo Lei, quali di questi settori sono più vulnerabili agli effetti del cambiamento climatico?

54 responses

Secondo Lei, il suo Comune è pronto ad affrontare i seguenti rischi climatici?

Secondo Lei, quali tipi di interventi potrebbero aiutare il territorio della Valcerrina ad affrontare meglio i cambiamenti climatici?

54 responses

Nella Sua attività o vita quotidiana, ha già adottato qualche misura per adattarsi a fenomeni come siccità, caldo intenso, allagamenti o incendi?

54 responses

Quali ostacoli rendono difficile l'adattamento nella Sua zona o attività?

54 responses

Survey 2 targeting the technical offices of the 12 member municipalities

Responses are being currently collected, and results have not been analyzed yet.

List of questions (in English)

1. Name and surname
2. Institution/role
3. Municipality
4. Email or phone contact
5. Does your municipality have a Municipal Civil Protection Plan?
6. When was it last updated?
7. Are the following risks included in the plan? [floods, heavy rainfall, forest fires, landslides, heatwaves, drought]
8. Who did you turn to for drafting or updating the Municipal Civil Protection Plan?
9. Which of these data sources and information did you use to draft the Plan (choose all that apply)?
10. What other information would you need to draft or update the Plan?
11. Is there already a community approach (Union of Municipalities of Valcerrina) to risk prevention and management?
12. If not, do you believe it could be efficient and useful for all municipalities?
13. How would you evaluate the drafting of an Inter-municipal Civil Protection Plan for the Union of Municipalities of Valcerrina?
14. Other comments regarding the drafting of the Municipal Civil Protection Plan and the community approach to risk management?
15. How relevant do you consider these risks for your municipality? [floods, heavy rainfall, forest fires, landslides, heatwaves, drought]
16. Any historical events of heavy rain, floods, forest fires, drought, or heatwaves in your municipality in the last 20 years (year, location, estimated damage, and any evacuations)?
17. Are there areas particularly at risk?
18. Do you think you have all the necessary information to manage these risks? [floods, heavy rainfall, forest fires, landslides, heatwaves, drought]
19. If not, what information are you missing?
20. As a municipality, do you feel ready to manage these risks? [floods, heavy rainfall, forest fires, landslides, heatwaves, drought]
21. If not, what measures would help you better manage these risks?
22. Are there other risks you consider relevant for your municipality?

23. What prevention, protection, or climate risk adaptation actions have been implemented in your municipality in the last 10 years?
24. What actions do you consider a priority to include or strengthen in the next Municipal Civil Protection Plan?
25. For your municipality, how adequate do you consider each of the following aspects for effective climate risk management? (Choose from 1 to 5, where 1 is very inadequate and 5 is fully adequate)
 - [Specialized municipal technical staff]
 - [Trained volunteer groups for emergency interventions]
 - [Awareness-raising of the local population on potential risks]
 - [Technical equipment (alert systems, sensors, drones, GIS software)]
 - [Updated data on risks and vulnerabilities]
 - [Equipment and tools for rapid interventions]
 - [Funds for prevention and risk management works]
 - [Effective legislative framework]
26. Which institutions or organizations do you actively collaborate with for risk prevention and management?
27. How do you evaluate the support received from the following bodies in prevention and risk management?
 - [Piedmont Region]
 - [Province of Alessandria]
 - [National Civil Protection Department]
28. Have you encountered critical issues between civil protection plans (municipal or regional) and operational reality? (e.g. difficult procedures, unavailable resources, inconsistencies between documents)
29. In what ways are citizens involved in climate risk prevention and management activities?
30. Which population groups have been involved or informed in the last 5 years?
31. Which communication tools are used to inform the population about climate risks and emergency measures?
32. Suggestions or proposals to improve community involvement